

Nature of ortho effect in the oxidation of *ortho*-substituted-benzaldehydes with pyridinium chlorochromate

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Rate constants for the oxidation reaction of *ortho*-substituted benzaldehydes with pyridinium chlorochromate are correlated with equations,

$$\log k_2 = \alpha\sigma_1 + \beta\sigma_R + \Psi v + h$$

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to detect the presence of steric effects. The results indicate that there is definite inductive, resonance and steric effects operating in the reaction. In some reactions, steric effect outweighs the electrical effect, while in others electrical effect is predominant.

The nature of ortho effect and its composition have been studied by many authors¹. They have given varying degrees of electrical and steric effects operating in the reaction. When the side-chain becomes sufficiently large, the substituent and the reaction site are no longer close to each other to permit the existence of the proximity effect. The aim of this work is to study the effect of *ortho*-substituents on the oxidation of benzaldehydes with pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC). A systematic study and multiparameter linear regression analysis on the influence of *ortho*-substituent on this reaction have been reported.

Results and Discussion

The second order rate constants (k_2) for the oxidation of *ortho*-substituted benzaldehydes with PCC at various temperatures and the thermodynamic parameters are presented in Table 1. The rate constants for all the *ortho*-substituents were found to be higher than unsubstituted benzaldehyde. The rates of oxidation did not give any significant correlation with either Taft's steric or polar substituent constants. Thus the observed reactivity is not compatible with either the size of the substituents or their Taft's polar substituent constants. In view of this, the rates were

analysed using Charton's method². The rate constants were correlated with equations (1) and (2), where σ_1 , σ_R and v are inductive, resonance and steric substituent constants respectively, and the values were those compiled by Aslam *et al.*³,

$$\log k_2 = \alpha\sigma_1 + \beta\sigma_R + \Psi v + h \quad (1)$$

$$\log k_2 = \alpha\sigma_1 + \beta\sigma_R + h \quad (2)$$

Multiple regression analysis was done for six substituents and equation (1) takes the form,

$$\log k_2 = 0.17\alpha\sigma_1 - 0.20\beta\sigma_R + 0.22\Psi v - 2.5357 \quad (3)$$

$$R = 0.9812, SD = 0.081, f = 0.034, F = 2.31, t = 2.63$$

The correlation with equation (1) was performed with the rate data obtained at different temperatures and the results are summarised in Table 2. The significance of correlation was tested by means of an F test⁴. The confidence levels of the F test are less than 90%. The confidence level for the significance of α , β and Ψ terms was evaluated by means of a student's 't' test⁴. The confidence level of the 't' test is about 95%. The results indicate that inductive, resonance and steric effects are operating considerably in the oxida-

Table 1. Second order rate constants and thermodynamic parameters for the oxidation of *ortho*-substituted-benzaldehydes with pyridinium chlorochromate

<i>o</i> -Substituent	$10^3 k_2, \text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$				ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
	303 K	313 K	323 K	333 K			
H	3.13	5.39	9.13	14.8	40.2	155	89.5
CH ₃	3.76	7.34	14.1	25.1	50.6	124	90.2
OCH ₃	5.48	9.49	15.5	25.2	39.9	157	89.7
Cl	4.56	7.24	10.7	16.3	32.7	182	90.6
Br	3.89	6.52	10.6	17.1	38.7	164	90.7
NO ₂	6.85	10.8	15.9	23.3	31.4	183	89.5

Table 2. Temperature dependence of the reaction constants for the oxidation of *ortho*-substituted-benzaldehydes by PCC

Temp. K	α	β	Ψ	R	SD	P_R	P_s
303	0.17	-0.20	0.22	0.9812	0.081	54.1	37.3
313	0.15	-0.19	0.20	0.9887	0.043	55.9	37.0
323	0.14	-0.17	0.19	0.9904	0.032	54.8	38.0
333	0.12	-0.14	0.16	0.9896	0.038	53.8	38.1

tion of *ortho*-substituted benzaldehydes. To test the significance of σ_1 and σ_R when ν is included, multiple regression analyses were carried out with σ_1 and ν with σ_R and ν . A non-linear correlation was obtained showing that both σ_1 and σ_R are significant. Considering the steric effect as constant, the multiple regression analysis was carried out with only σ_1 and σ_R . The results show very poor correlation,

$$\log k_2 = 0.35 \sigma_1 - 0.06 \sigma_R - 2.4719 \quad (4)$$

$$R = 0.7760, SD = 0.077, f = 0.033, F = 2.26, t = 2.13$$

The contribution of the resonance effect² to the polar effect is given in equation (5),

$$P_R = \frac{100 \times |\beta|}{|\alpha| + |\beta|} \quad (5)$$

The contribution of the steric parameter² to the total effect of the substituent, P_s , was determined using equation (6),

$$P_s = \frac{100 \times |\Psi|}{|\alpha| + |\beta| + |\Psi|} \quad (6)$$

The values of P_R and P_s are recorded in Table 2. The values of P_R show that the resonance effect is more dominant than the inductive effect. The P_R for the *para*-position is 50% by definition¹. The observed value of P_R (ca 54%) in the case of *ortho*-substituents shows that the balance of the inductive and resonance effects is different for the *ortho*- and *para*-positions, the resonance effect being more pronounced in the *ortho* case. This may be due to the coplanarity of the aldehyde group with the benzene ring containing the *ortho*-substituent.

The value of P_s (ca 37%) shows that there is considerable steric effect in this reaction but it is subordinate to the electrical effect. The positive value of Ψ indicates the steric acceleration of the rate⁵. In the mechanistic study of the oxidation of benzaldehydes with PCC, an ester formation is proposed in the rate-limiting step⁶. To avoid more crowding in the ester, the *ortho*-substituent takes a preferred orientation that is more coplanar with the benzene ring (1).

1

There are two opposing polar effects, viz. +I and -M effects for the methoxy group. According to Ingold⁷, the +I effect of the *ortho*-methoxy group usually outweighs the -M effect and hence one would expect these compounds to be less reactive than benzaldehyde. However, it is not so. The observed higher rate can very well be explained on the basis of the phenomenon of steric enhancement of resonance. The free rotation of the OCH₃ group is restricted and it is more coplanar with the benzene ring.

For the methyl substituent in the *ortho*-position there is only a smaller electrical effect⁸. The primary steric effect may outweigh the electrical effect. This gives a rate for *ortho*-methyl slightly higher than that of benzaldehyde. The higher rate constants for the halogens and nitro group may be due to the operation of both electrical effect and the steric enhancement of resonance.

The entropy of activation is found to be more negative for all the *ortho*-substituted benzaldehydes. Generally, a bulky substituent near the reaction centre will reduce the number of energy levels available to the transition state to those in the initial state and this renders ΔS^\ddagger more negative⁹. This indicates that the transition states are more crowded and rigid. The crowding increases the energy content of the reactant ester due to a greater loss of degrees of freedom when the molecule goes to the transition state.

Experimental

Benzaldehyde, *o*-methyl-, *o*-chloro- and *o*-bromobenzaldehydes (E. Merck) were purified by repeated distillation. *o*-Nitrobenzaldehyde (B.D.H.) was purified by recrystallisation. Pyridinium chlorochromate was prepared using reported procedure¹⁰. Double-distilled water and purified acetic acid were used. All other chemicals were AnalaR grade and used as such.

The rate measurements were carried out in 50% aqueous acetic acid (v/v) at four temperatures (303, 313, 323 and 333 K). Perchloric acid was used as the catalyst and sodium perchlorate used for maintaining ionic strength. The reactions were initiated by mixing appropriate volumes of thermally pre-equilibrated reactant solutions under pseudo-first order conditions, [Aldehyde] \gg [PCC]. The progress of the reaction was followed by iodometric determination of the unreacted PCC. The rate constants were determined by the least-squares method.

Note

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